

Are Countries Allowing Communities to Lead? The Global Landscape of National Civil Society Laws and their Association with HIV 95-95-95 Indicators

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Background: Civil society organizations (CSOs) are essential for the HIV/AIDS response. CSOs mobilize communities, engage with marginalized and key populations, and participate in advocacy efforts to address AIDS-related stigma and discrimination, and in service delivery by ensuring access to treatment services and treatment adherence support. National laws dictate whether CSOs can register and operate freely and whether CSOs can receive government funds to provide services and are hypothesized to matter in the AIDS response. The actual effect of these laws, however, has not been shown or measured. This study provides an overview of global adoption of civil society related laws and tests their association with HIV 95-95-95 targets.

Methodology: Text of laws and legal information was collected by the HIV Policy Lab through in-depth legal and policy review for 194 countries from 2017-2023. Laws were coded by legal experts to measure two indicators: i) presence of social contracting policies for financing CSOs and ii) capability of CSOs to register and operate freely under national law. Countries were coded as 'Adopted' (both indicators adopted), 'Partially Adopted' (one adopted) and 'Not Adopted' (neither adopted). Using a cross-sectional dataset, fractional logistic regression was used to determine associations between the adoption of CSO laws and HIV 95-95-95 indicators.

Results: The number of countries that adopted and partially adopted Civil Society policies has significantly increased between 2017 (n=85, 70.8%) and 2023 (n=90, 84.1%) ($\chi^2(1, N=227)=4.9$, $p<0.05$). Results from fractional logistic regression show that the odds of PLHIV knowing their HIV status increases by a factor of almost 2 in countries which have adopted civil society freedom policies compared to countries without civil society freedom policies and legislation [OR:1.899, 95%CI:1.42-2.53, $p<0.0001$].

Conclusion: Legislation and freedom policies for civil society impact national ability to reach AIDS targets. The adoption of national laws supporting both CSO operational freedom and social contracting should be a priority for the global AIDS response. Tracking the national policy environments for CSOs is an important step to ensuring that countries adopt policies that reduce the burden of HIV/AIDS, both nationally and globally.